

ANALYZING DIFFERENT SOFTWARE PROJECT MANAGEMENT TOOLS AND PROPOSING A NEW PROJECT MANAGEMENT TOOL USING PROCESS RE-ENGINEERING ON OPEN-SOURCE AND SAAS PLATFORMS FOR A DEVELOPING COUNTRY LIKE BANGLADESH

¹SAIKAT BAUL,²MD. RATAN RANA, ³SAKIMUL KARIM ADAN, ⁴NAZIA TAFANNUM, ⁵FARZANA ALAM

^{1,2,3,4} Student, American International University-Bangladesh, 408/1, Kuratoli, Khilkhet, Dhaka 1229, Bangladesh.

⁵Lecturer, American International University-Bangladesh, 408/1, Kuratoli, Khilkhet, Dhaka 1229, Bangladesh

E-mail: ¹saikatbaul.cs@gmail.com, ²ratanrana9684@gmail.com, ³sakimuladan680@gmail.com,
⁴naziat913@gmail.com, ⁵farzana.alam@aiub.edu

Abstract - This paper analyzes and evaluates different software project management tools that help the team to plan, manage, optimize resources, and monitor the project progress. The ICT industry in Bangladesh has immense prospects in driving the country's economy, and it has grown by 28%-40% annually since 2010 each year. But though we have huge benefits over low development costs, clients of the developed country are not very satisfied with the quality of the software. So in this paper, we are proposing an open source-based project management tool that will serve small to medium-sized software firms at no cost. The software firms will maintain the software engineering best practices by using the software. As "openness" becomes one of society's hallmarks in the 21st century and extends into innovation, research, and standards-setting, an open-source system has become an integral part of the business. Because of the speed and the scale at which it has happened, open-source is central to strategy today. But we do not have any cloud access in an Open-source system. For that reason, in this paper, we also have tried to propose the same tool with more options in the Software as a Service (SaaS) environment.

Keywords - Project Management Tool, Process Reengineering, Open-source, Software as a Service.

I. INTRODUCTION

Project management tool is software that deals with the project plan, execution, monitoring project progress over time and cost, and managing resources. Project management tools help organizations save 28x more money than organizations that do not use tools. But useful project management tools are not always free, and the features are scattered. All the tools serve these purposes quite well, but these tools do not work together and often do not sync properly.

Project management tools with Open-source or SaaS are available for a free or high cost. Still, those are not always feasible for small to medium software companies, especially with a lower budget in developing countries like Bangladesh.

Open source has been pushed in a new direction by the cloud. The features are strategic to provide the option to fork the code tree for companies, and it goes off in directions that diminish the value. Using open-source improves the speed you can market, prevents seller lock-in, and lowers costs.

A software program that is licensed for utilizing a cloud-based business model is known as a SaaS application [9]. Rather than using a desktop program, most businesses now offer Software as a Service. They can subscribe to specific services among many available services monthly or annually. Business Process Re-engineering is a cost-effective way to enhance or change the software's features and improve product quality. It reduces software costs,

improves quality, improves customer service, and reduces delivery time.

We have come to know that there are over 500 registered software and Information Technology Enabled Services (ITES) companies in Bangladesh. More than 100 firms are exporting their products to over 30 countries. At least 30 of these 100 companies are jointly working with foreign companies where these foreign companies are 100% principal investors [18]. Since we have a meager cost of software development and maintenance, Bangladesh holds higher precedence in the software industry in the world. Still, because of the IT infrastructure, lower budget, and other difficulties, the quality of our software projects is not top-notch. In this paper, we have analyzed different features of different software project management tools and proposed a new tool that will help software industries in underdeveloped or developing countries like Bangladesh by offering a low budget software project management tool where different types of project development phases will be covered in one place using open-source or SaaS platform.

II. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

A) Important Project Management Process

The motivation behind project management tool is to design and deal a project to effectively achieve its required objectives and meet expectations. Some important Project management processes are-

- 1) **Project Integration Management:** It encompasses all the steps involved in identifying, defining, merging, unifying, and managing several processes and project management activities inside the management process groups [4][6]. Performing Integration Management in a project is to keep the total interconnected project as one bound together an arrangement of exercises.
- 2) **Project Scope Management:** The act of producing a plan that clearly describes how the project scope will be developed, assessed, and maintained[4][6].
- 3) **Project Time Management:** Analyzing and setting a timeframe for project completion[5][6]. Unexpected bottlenecks and miscalculated project timeframes are buffered by formalized time management techniques.
- 4) **Project Cost Management:** It includes the estimation, allocation, and control of project expenditures. Cost estimates are established during the planning stage of a project and should be authorized before work can begin and be monitored throughout the project life cycle.
- 5) **Project Quality Management:** The practice of continuously monitoring the quality of the whole operations and taking top actions until the top quality is assured is known as project quality management [5].
- 6) **Project Resource Management:** It is securing, distributing and dealing with the assets like people and their skills, funds, innovation, materials, apparatus and regular assets [6].
- 7) **Project Communication Management:** It is the methodical preparation, carrying out, observing, and correction of the relative multitude of channels of communication with an association and between associations [4][6].
- 8) **Project Risk Management:** It is the process through which project managers manage hazards that might have a positive or negative impact on a project [5][6]. The aim is to reduce the severity of these dangers.
- 9) **Project Stakeholder Management:** It is a project management technique that involves managing all of the internal and external stakeholders involved in a project's expectations and requirements [4][5].
- 10) **Project Defect Management:** A software defect is a bug or error in the program that causes incorrect or unexpected results from the actual

output expectation. Software defect management is a process of detecting bugs and fixing them.

B) Important Features of Project Management Tools

Project management tools help to keep a streamlined flow in the project management process. Some important features of project management tools [4] are-

- 1) **Customize fields** allow you to tailor the fields in your project management software to your own business and project requirements.
- 2) **API or Application Programming Interface** enables the sharing of data and application between devices.
- 3) **The Project Management tools** must allow for collaboration so the whole team can work together. Collaboration not only makes the task easier, but also increases the productivity of the project.
- 4) **Risk analysis** is a method for identifying and managing potential issues that could risk important company initiatives or projects.
- 5) **Project Planning** when you do the project work you have to do the project planning. In fact planning is one of the most important phases or aspects of the project.
- 6) **Work breakdown structure** identifies scope for a project, we break that down into different activities and tasks.
- 7) **Schedule Planning** is another important activity to actually help us in approaching the schedule planning activities properly.
- 8) **Financial planning** is involved with budgeting aspects of the project apart from that how are we going to release funds on the project.
- 9) **Test Management Tools** visualize trends over the time to assist developers in quickly identifying errors and flaws in software.
- 10) **Gantt chart or Schedule** is a bar chart that shows the tasks of a project, when each must take place and how long each will take. As the project progresses, bars are shaded to indicate the completed tasks.
- 11) **Comments and notes** are where clients can share data and leave messages about reports, organizers, libraries, and subsides.

C) Popular Softwares in The Industry

There are many project management tools in the software industry but some of them are extremely popular for their features. They are Monday.com, Wrike, Jira, Trello, Asana, Teamwork, Meister task,

Basecamp, Oracle primavera, MS Project, MS SharePoint, MS Visio, etc.

1) Popular project management tools with Best Features:

Figure 1: Best Features of Existing Software.

The top features of Monday.com are building custom workflows across teams, monitoring, managing, and tracking workloads [12]. It allows accessible communication, collaboration, and data visualization.

Wrike is one of the most popular project management tools having some best features like organized file management, easy time tracking, real-time reporting, efficient task management, and a visual timeline [13].

Jira is primarily famous for its issue tracking system. Jira can also support Agile teams to plan, build, track progress, and has all the features you need for efficient task management, reporting, and team collaboration[12].

The best features of Trello are detailed and quick overviews of front-back cards, Drag-and-Drop or inline editing, easy upload, automated email

notifications, group task assignment, deadline alerts [14].

The best features of Asana are templates, keeping projects organized, meeting deadlines, checking project progress, tracking individual tasks, planning sprints, integrating with other tools, creating custom reports, and adding tasks[15].

Teamwork's best features are supporting multiple projects, group tasks by projects, managing expenses, making task lists, tracking time, uploading files, instant messaging, and social collaboration platform. [16].

MeisterTask helps to automate repetitive tasks[12]. People can drag and drop tasks on the timeline for instant task scheduling and generate quick or customized reports, and the dashboard shows an all-in-one overview of daily work.

Using Basecamp, people can create tasks, set deadlines, and assign them to team members[12].

The best features of oracle primavera are project status email updates, risk management, information dashboard, configurable form, and graphical workflow modeling [17].

The best features of MS projects are planning and scheduling, project timeline view, collaboration, reporting, resource management, multiple projects, different views [12].

Proof Hub is a versatile project management tool with a scalable solution for managing project activities where managers control the project. Its features include tracking time, team chat, data security, safe telecommunication, collaboration, project planning, and reporting. ProofHub 2022 is 100% cloud-based[19].

Scoro is acknowledged among the widest variety of small to medium sized business management solutions hosted in the cloud, where projects, clients, and teams can all be found in a spot[19]. With a seamless workflow, the program has several useful functions such as real-time overview, automated reports, customized dashboard and invoice system, task tracking, and schedule that is an essential element of business.

Workzone is one of the finest project management tools with some quality features like top-level reports, faster communication system, create tasks, improved to-do list, and top-level file-sharing system with permission system[19]. ProProfs is a simple project management tool that brings all our projects under one roof. We can share files, discuss roadblocks, give feedback, get real-time notification, drag and drop

functionality, invoice generation and manage billable and non-billable hours[19].

GhanttPRO enables users to create project plans and timetables, track workflow, manage budgets and adhere to deadlines. Gantt charts, bar charts, customized visualization, drag and drop, and a board view are available in the workspace and easy-to-use project templates[19]. Maintain a balanced workload by keeping all resources engaged while Comments, attachments, and alerts are all examples of collaboration.

2)Shortcomings of the Best available Project management tools:

Most Clients of Monday are happy with the product. However, some users have difficulties creating a team. It misses automation between different boards, the platform gets slow when there is a lot for it to display, and the menus are not intuitive and helpful[12].

Wrike has a long expectation to learn and adapt. Still, it is overwhelming for new users. Adding new users and assigning tasks to them is difficult[13], customizing dashboard view is unavailable, slow to load systems, upload or download files, and task prioritization is not available.

Moving a task, for instance, from Microsoft Team Foundation Server into Jira includes physically moving every curio into Jira, which is extremely tedious. Clients cannot download Jira graphical reports as pictures [12].

Trello is not an entirely complete project management tool or a best agile tool. Communication is not significantly improved, Trello has integration limitations like it does not have an import function, and Trello doesn't show task dependencies[14].

Asana does not have a time tracking feature, and new users need previous experience using other project management tools. It is not best for small teams or a single project, and it has too many features to overwhelm its users[15].

Teamwork falls short of the in-depth analysis and reporting provided by competing systems; feature visualization, chat features are not available [16].

MeisterTask does not have a lot of command over the association of the projects, does not have a timeline view of the to-do list of tasks, mobile version crashes often, and no calendar view[12].

Basecamp doesn't permit you to put a tag or mark, does not have time tracking, and the user interface is not intuitive[12].

Primavera P6 is for Windows, which puts Mac clients neglected [17]. P6 is unwieldy for more modest, and less complex tasks intrigued uniquely in the more extensive venture area. For joint effort, in the Microsoft project, you might need to utilize Outlook, Skype, or other correspondence applications from Microsoft[12]. The most recent MS Project additionally needs Windows 10 to run the work area application.

ProofHub is pretty easy to get up, but it can improve a bit in helping people customize their accounts more. It has limited integration with other software with too many notifications. Proofing functionality is minimal, and sometimes messages disappear automatically[20]. Scoro's pricing approach is designed for larger companies, but it might be crippling for smaller ones. People will never be aware of hidden charges until it is too late to make a difference. Scoro's integrations with other systems are restricted. Although APIs are accessible, they are not suitable for all applications[20].

Workzone does not have a lot of issues, but it is pretty tricky to use if the user is new. It also has a problem with to-do list sync[20].

In ProProfs, there are too many limitations to customize the product from a learning perspective. It needs to add more templates and be customizable[20]. Uploading images, audio, and video is time-consuming. There should be an improvement in executive status reports of projects, dashboard-like reports for team meetings, birds-eye view, burn-down, burn-up, charts, and other metrics for the tasks and general. GhanttPRO is super slow to load, with limited integration with other applications. It may be a little expensive for students worldwide [20].

III. METHODOLOGY

Software reengineering is the most common process of updating a software. This interaction remembers fostering essential features for the product and adding/dropping functionalities for better and more proficient software [1]. In an ever-evolving world, software products must be adaptable and flexible to keep the clients fulfilled and drawn in for quite a while. Arrangements are getting increasingly more intricate to meet high client requirements. The project management team ought to be upheld by many tools to execute tasks effectively. These tools can be explicitly planned devices or conventional useful apparatuses that can be embraced for project execution [2].

In this paper, we re-evaluated many project management tools by researching many features but did not find any fully complete project management tool. For that reason, a software management tool is

suggested here that combines all the project management tools and has all the features needed to complete a project. This proposal is for both under developing and developing countries because this management tool is on Open Source and Software as a Service (SaaS). We want SaaS so that it gives full access to this tool. Because in Open Source, we cannot provide all access like cloud access. The research of this paper intends to follow the exploratory qualitative research approach. Data collection is based on the existing literature and secondary data collected from the internet based on customer reviews to extract required information for the research. Qualitative analysis is checked to address the strategic benefits of SaaS and Open-Source Software. The principal methods used in this study were observation and review. We didn't find any models for quality in the international standards that adequately reflect the quality attributes in the system. Keeping these in mind, the concept and description of a model that considers criteria and quality standards specific to SaaS applications built on Open-Source Software were required. "Open source" is a concept that denotes the class of the software in which the source code is freely available for intending contributors or code reviewers [8]. It is usually a collaborative effort where software developers in different locations of the world access the source codes and make needed contributions with the overall goal of improving the quality of the software. We intend to provide capacity for the adaptation and customization of Open-Source Software. The implementation will eliminate the enormous financial burden accruing from software development outsourcing, reduce the rate of transcription errors arising from paper-based tools, save paper and storage space, improve staff performance, and extend the functionalities to support facility-based data collection. Subsequent sections will address solutions used in the past, the advantages, and associated problems. It shall further work on suggested methods for its easy adaptation and implementation.

The relevance of the requirements of the attributes has indicated which characteristics are fundamental based on knowledge and practical experience. The service models of cloud computing represent different models used with the deployment models that include the software as a Service (SaaS).

IV. PROPOSED FEATURES OF OUR PROJECT MANAGEMENT TOOL

Our proposed project management tool offers the key features of both SaaS and Open-Source based software.

1)Project Integration Management: To ensure the organization's growth, the collaboration software

should allow you to manage projects and track if all activities are done within set deadlines. We can share our screen for better communication with team members. Among other remote work OS, incorporates different outsider applications to smooth out information stream and collaboration across client's work environment called Integration. Straightforward sharing and consistent joint effort, engages collaboration with dynamic and useful group locales for each task group, office, and division. For simple project management executions, it allows clients to automate different assignments, such as recurring tasks, and smooth out work processes. An application program interface (API) is the arrangement of timeline creating, tracking, conventions, and instruments utilized for building programming applications. The dashboard offers visualization of task lists and many more features.

2)Project Scope Management: For project planning, first, we need to determine the project scope that aids in identifying and tracking a comprehensive list among all project goals, tasks, deliverables, deadlines, and budgets. It's natural in project management for a large-scale project to undergo changes and updates. This is much simpler and easier for project teams to supervise and ensure correct improvements when the project management scope is set right at the beginning.

3)Project Requirement management: A work breakdown structure or WBS is a task list that adopts a bit-by-bit strategy to finish enormous activities with a few moving pieces. We list all the requirements from the stakeholders and users, use change control processes, project backlog, Sprint backlog, etc. Other project-related ideas or suggestions are maintained here in the Notes section, along with the person's name.

4)Project Time Management: Analyzing and establishing a timeframe and schedule for project implementation is part of project time management. When the client begins a project, they will click on the clock in the column to start the following time for that errand. Calendar organizes almost everything in place, and assembles all of your events, chores, and accomplishments all in one spot. Project Scheduling for project management is posting exercises, expectations, and achievements inside a task. Gantt charts are a successful instrument for administering work in task list. They are utilized to design tasks, everything being equal, and shapes. Deadline Management is an interaction where project administrators sort out, focus on, and plan their responsibility within a restricted time.

5)Project cost management: Across the whole project life cycle, project cost management is the process of forecasting, planning, and optimizing expenses with

the goal of staying within the agreed budget. Create Budgets on board can be utilized to follow sum and date for every single repeating charge.

6)Project Quality Management: The practice of continuously monitoring the quality of all operations and taking corrective action until the required quality is attained is known as project quality management. A project's quality management also decreases the potential of malfunctions or customer's dissatisfaction. In this we have, activity tracking is observing the advancement of a task to assess if it is gaining the right headway to accomplish the concurred goals or results. Testing helps individuals to check the functionalities whether it works as it is supposed to and how well it performs. Issue Tracking is used to follow up with bugs and component demands during item improvement.

7)Project Resource Management: Resource management is getting, distributing, and dealing with the assets, for example, people and their skills, accounts, innovation, materials, hardware, and regular assets needed for a task. Document storage that records stockpiling demonstrates putting an archive, usually a computerized report, into a library in the executive's framework. Automatic backup and Data synchronization forestall information clashes.

8)Project Communication Management: Project communication management is a set of measures for helping to ensure that the required interactions are transmitted, acknowledged, and interpreted by the respective respondents. Notification Management assists you with guaranteeing the exact conveyance of essential data to the perfect individual at the ideal opportunity and many more communication features.

9)Project Risk Management: Risk management involves the process of detecting, analyzing, and mitigating or controlling risks to a project that may have the ability to threaten the best output in project management. We have features like, Security, with regards to project management, can in this way be characterized as the distinguishing proof of possible dangers and execution of methodologies. In risk management, project managers can undoubtedly distinguish when dangers might happen, and the effect of these dangers in the project standard and timetable.

10) Project Stakeholder Management: Identification of stakeholders, the study of their expectations and influences, the creation of appropriate methods to engage with stakeholders, and the execution of the process is all part of project stakeholder management. A project management framework based on a CRM stage permits groups to effortlessly get errands and tasks that identify with developing the client relationship.

Figure 2: Proposed Features List

V. RESULT & DISCUSSION

Practical methods are required at every stage of the open-source software development management tool, from planning to implementation to completion. Project management software is essential for organizing and controlling numerous project components at each step of the project's life cycle. Organizations with several projects and large teams may experience difficulties integrating their project works. Many responsibilities, such as creativity, planning, implementation, testing, delivery, and maintenance, necessitate the participation of teams. And each phase is vital for producing a high-quality product and keeping clients happy, both of which are important for business growth. We already have

bunches of helpful project management tools. Still, in our research, we have found that users mostly complain about a complete-featured project management tool and found this tool should synchronize well with other project management tools. We have not found any project management tool that serves the purpose. Also, we found from our study that developing or under-developed countries are good places for IT industry investment for developed countries. But due to poor software qualities, we are not competing well with software industries in India or Asian countries. So, after evaluating the situation, we thought of building a tool that will consist of all the essential project management features. Small to medium software firms can use this tool and make quality products at

little to no cost. In such a way, our software industries can get more overseas projects and contribute more to our revenue.

For this reason, our open-source software development management tool aids in the full completion of a project's procedure. It allows us to optimize each stage to complete projects on schedule and with high quality. It strengthens your relationship with our customers, fosters trust, and aids in the maintenance of a positive brand image. We may streamline our workflow over the whole project lifetime by employing an open-source software development management tool. The software firms will save time and effort by automating time-consuming and unpleasant manual procedures.

On the other hand, our proposed tool may be used to automate various tasks. We can easily delegate work, organize tasks appropriately, monitor implementation, assess progress, combine other tools you already use, and take advantage of extra features to accomplish our projects in shorter turnaround times with top-notch quality. In the same circumstance, software firms might be interested in a self-hosted or SaaS-based project management platform. With the help of reengineering, we can add more valuable features to a single project management tool. The project team will find all features in this project management tool. And it is also time-efficient for the project team. It optimizes the database and productivity also, so its processing gets faster. This acclimates the developer's thinking to seizing new chances, allowing for developing increasingly new features. Rather than constructing a software product from the base, developers improve an existing product to enhance some key characteristics relevant to stakeholders or consumers. This type of exercise lowers the likelihood of fault fallibility. This procedure refines the system's features and functions while reducing the product's complexity to the greatest extent possible.

Instead of purchasing software or additional equipment to support it, customers subscribe to a SaaS service. Many organizations can improve and forecast their budgeting by converting expenditures to recurrent operational expenses. To avoid recurrent charges, SaaS subscriptions can be terminated at any moment. Vertical scalability is a feature of cloud services such as SaaS that allows users to access more or fewer services or features depending on their needs. Because SaaS providers distribute software via the internet, users may access SaaS programs from any internet-enabled device and location.

The system can be used to direct the inspiration, arranging, and dynamic parts of process re-engineering alongside organizing the product practices and supporting advances for executing the full range of re-engineering exercises. Traditional

project management tools secure essential scheduling, budgeting, and designating human and material assets. Project staff ought to be capable of such "hard" abilities as the rudiments of contracting, business finance, incorporated expense, and timetable control, estimating work execution, checking quality, and leading danger investigations. Likewise, they ought to be skillful at such "delicate" abilities as arranging, overseeing change, being politically insightful, and understanding the requirements and needs of individuals they manage.

Project management tools framework help groups or specialists and has demonstrated to be a solid and powerful framework for the management of projects. For that reason, the concentration in this paper aims to understand the prerequisites for project management tools with Open-source and SaaS advancement endeavors and how the improvement of these necessities contrasts from those conventional to software engineering. Subsequently, these are used to understand what project management tools communities are being examined and what characteristics distinguish one community from another. With the help of the software reuse technique, packaged modules for project booking and detailing were determined, analyzed, designed, and conveyed into the central system. The re-engineering procedure helped change the center framework to allow the expansion of an information assortment device. A layout for recording all project works was planned and implemented into the framework. Customization of the User Interface and module will likewise be executed. Effective execution of this re-engineered application, the project management tool, can assist with reinforcing the project capacities in Bangladesh.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper discussed an approach for a Re-engineered software development Management tool on an Open-Source Platform upgraded to Software as a Service (SaaS) Platform. This work aims to provide guidelines on how to re-engineering Open-Source Software in a SaaS platform. At the time of writing, we have provided several examples and suggestions of reviewing topmost software, which are based on the SaaS platform and Open-Source Software separately. This study investigates several aspects of Open-Source Software and SaaS adoption in the vertical software development industry. This worldview has gotten considerable attention in recent works, even though it represents a large section of the software industry. Examining the many aspects of vertical sectors may disclose specific components that explain adoption or non-adoption that do not appear in purchasing more generalized software. Many sophisticated software design methodologies have been established to improve the recyclability

and manageability of software and minimize the time necessary for maintenance and development operations. Yet, many organizations still have old or legacy software systems that cost a lot of money to maintain. Because these systems contain implicit knowledge and judgments, they cannot be replaced by new systems. Re-engineering becomes a successful approach for converting viable ways of transforming old, inefficient systems into more efficient, streamlined systems.

In the future, we want to work on the implemented software based on our proposal and look for more improvement as much as we can suggest because the world wants improvements every new day. A deep understanding of the problem itself is not necessary before intervention. The different iterations used by the developers to evaluate the problem may take considerable time and conscience, which will open another field of new research. These results of the study conducted outcomes that will be researched further. The findings suggest the unique adoption of the patterns on distinct systems, which is beneficial for conceptual frameworks in the software industry.

REFERENCE

- [1] Ahmed Abbas, Wilson Jeberson, and V.V. Klinsega. 2012. The Need for Re-engineering in Software Engineering. *International Journal of Engineering and Technology* 2049-3444 2, (February 2012).
- [2] John Bergey, William Hefley, Walter Lamia, and Dennis Smith. 1995. A Reengineering Process Framework. *Software Engineering Institute, Carnegie Mellon University.*–Pittsburgh (1995).
- [3] Yan Liu, Qingling Wang, Mingguang Zhuang, and Yunyun Zhu. 2008. Reengineering Legacy Systems with RESTful Web Service. In 2008 32nd Annual IEEE International Computer Software and Applications Conference, 785–790. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1109/COMPSAC.2008.89>
- [4] Quynh Le Hua Xuan, Massoud Moslehpour, and Dat Tran. 2019. An evaluation of project management tools and techniques in Vietnam. *Management Science Letters* 9, (February 2019), 283–300. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2018.11.011>
- [5] Peerasit Patanakul. 2010. An Empirical Study on the use of Project Management Tools and Techniques across Project Life-Cycle and their Impact on Project Success. *Journal of General Management* 35, (March 2010), 41–65. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1177/030630701003500304>
- [6] Project Management Institute. 2017. A guide to the project management body of knowledge (pmbok(r) guide)-sixth edition. Project Management Institute.
- [7] Valentina Lenarduzzi, Davide Taibi, Davide Tosi, Luigi Lavazza, and Sandro Morasca. 2020. Open Source Software Evaluation, Selection, and Adoption: a Systematic Literature Review. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1109/SEAA51224.2020.00076>
- [8] Alfonso Fuggetta. 2003. Open source software - An evaluation. *Journal of Systems and Software* 66, (April 2003), 77–90. DOI:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0164-1212\(02\)00065-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0164-1212(02)00065-1)
- [9] Audris Mockus, Roy Fielding, and James Herbsleb. 2002. Two Case Studies of Open Source Software Development: Apache and Mozilla. *ACM Transactions on Software Engineering and Methodology* 11, (September 2002). DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1145/567793.567795>
- [10] Manish Godse and Shrikant Mulik. 2009. An Approach for Selecting Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) Product. In *CLOUD 2009 - 2009 IEEE International Conference on Cloud Computing*, 155–158. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1109/CLOUD.2009.74>
- [11] Michael Cusumano. 2010. Cloud Computing and SaaS as New Computing Platforms. *Commun. ACM* 53, (April 2010), 27–29. DOI:<https://doi.org/10.1145/1721654.1721667>
- [12] List of Top Project Management Software 2022. Retrieved September 14, 2021 from <https://www.trustradius.com/project-management>
- [13] Smiljanić, D., 2022. Wrike Project Management Pros and Cons - Binfire. [online] Binfire. Available at: <<https://www.binfire.com/blog/wrike-project-management-pros-cons/>> [Accessed 14 October 2021].
- [14] Team, P., 2022. Top 8 Disadvantages of Using Trello - ProjectManagers.NET. [online] ProjectManagers.NET. Available at: <<https://projectmanagers.net/top-8-disadvantages-of-using-trello/>> [Accessed 11 September 2021].
- [15] Project-Management.com. 2022. Advantages & Disadvantages of Asana 2022 | With Top Alternatives. [online] Available at: <<https://project-management.com/advantages-and-disadvantages-of-asana/>> [Accessed 1 September 2021].
- [16] Teamwork’s features. (n.d.). Teamwork.Com. Retrieved October 3, 2021, from <https://www.teamwork.com/project-management-software/features/>.
- [17] Oracle primavera-features. (n.d.). Oracle.Com. Retrieved October 20, 2021, from <https://www.oracle.com/industries/construction-engineering/primavera-p6/>.
- [18] Software and ICT Industry in Bangladesh. Retrieved September 9, 2021 from http://www.projectsprofile.com/posts/related_three.html
- [19] 54 Best Project Management Tools & Software for 2022: ProofHub. Retrieved September 21, 2021 from <https://www.proofhub.com/articles/top-project-management-tools-list>
- [20] Project Management Software 2022 - GetApp. Retrieved September 21, 2021 from <https://www.getapp.com/project-management-planning-software/project-management/>

